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Research Article

Comparative Study of Growth Performance, Food Utilization and Survival of Hatchery Bred and Wild Collected Fingerlings of African Catfish *Clarias gariepinus*

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ABSTRACT

Growth performance, food utilization and survival hatchery bred and wild collected fingerlings of African catfish, *Clarias gariepinus* was carried out as a comparative study with hatchery bred fingerlings for ten weeks in glass aquaria. Duplicate group of 10 with mean bulk weight 45.0 ± 0.0 g were stocked in four aquaria measuring 96 by 50 by 29cm³ labeled A1, A2, B1 and B2. Aquaria A1 and A2 were stocked with hatchery bred fingerlings (10 each) collected from the University of Calabar Hatchery Complex and Aquarium B1 and B2 were stocked with wild fingerlings (10 each) collected from Ayadehe Village (Itu Head Bridge). The experimental fish were fed with Coppens commercial feed twice daily at 5% of their body weight. Growth performance indices showed that weight gain (g), growth rate (GR), specific growth rate (SGR) and mean growth rate (MGR), percentage weight gain and percentage survival of hatchery collected *C. gariepinus* fingerlings was significantly different ($P < 0.05$) from wild collected fingerlings. Food utilisation indices showed that hatchery bred fingerlings consumed significantly ($P < 0.05$) more feed (993.15 ± 14.85 g) than wild collected fingerlings (617.75 ± 11.55) whereas food conversion ratio (FCR) and food conversion efficiency were not significantly different ($P > 0.05$). Proximate analysis of the experimental feed (Coppens feed) shows that moisture content was (8.23 ± 0.07), crude protein content (42.94 ± 1.34), lipid content (11.57 ± 0.15), crude fibre content (3.53 ± 0.31), ash content (9.42 ± 0.04) and carbohydrate content (24.31 ± 2.10). Physicochemical parameters including pH, water temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), dissolved oxygen (mg/L) and ammonia (mg/L) were controlled within the acceptable range for fresh water fish culture. The implication of this findings is that hatchery bred fingerlings of *C. gariepinus* is still the best source of fingerlings supply for fish farmers. It is concluded that fish farmers who still rely on wild fingerlings for fish farming will encounter poor growth performance and negative response to artificial feed leading to stunted fish, increase in culture period and reduction in expected profit margin. Therefore, hatchery bred fingerlings of *C. gariepinus* is recommended for a successful catfish farming.

Keywords: Growth performance; Food utilisation; *Clarias gariepinus*; hatchery bred fingerlings; wild fingerlings; survival.

INTRODUCTION

Fish is a reliable source of thiamine, riboflavin, vitamins A and D, phosphorus, calcium and iron (Eyo and Ekanem, 2011). In Nigeria, consumption and demand for fish protein is increasing due to its affordability. The African catfish *C. gariepinus* is a very popular fresh water fish in Nigeria (Eyo et al., 2012). It is regarded as one of the most important aquaculture candidates because of its ability to tolerate a wide range of environmental conditions, high stocking densities under culture conditions, fast growth rate, high yield potential, high fecundity, air breathing characteristics and high market value (Hetch et al., 1996; Babalola and Apatá, 2006).

Aquaculture is gaining attention all over the world as means of improving world fish production which is currently on decline due to dwindling output from capture fishery (FAO, 2003). FAO (2010) reported that growth rates for aquaculture production are slowing, reflecting the impacts of a wide range of factors. In Nigeria, unavailability of high quality *C. gariepinus* seed has been a major challenge faced by farmers and intending farmers, which has led to a decline in production rates. Of course, breeding has been developed for *C. gariepinus* seed, but production systems and hatchery management techniques that make catfish seed of high quality readily available to all farmers are yet to be established in most parts of African countries (Pouomogne et al., 1998; Brummentt et al., 2007). According to FAO (2010b), the procedures for *C. gariepinus* fingerlings production system are being simplified, but only a few farmers have been exposed to new methodology. Consequently, the price of catfish fingerlings remains high and most farmers prefer to collect wild seed when available but unfortunately, these fingerlings often consist of mixed species of *Clarias* and some, such as *C. jaensis*, which exhibit comparatively lower growth rates (FAO, 2010b). Alternatively, collection of wild seed of *C. gariepinus* provides a cheaper and partial solution to the above mentioned problem. A number of reports have described the traditional practice of enhancing the natural entry of wild fish into flood ponds, such as the “fingerponds” in Lake Victoria Wetlands (Unesco-IEH, 2005), and “whedoes” used in Benin and Togo (King, 1993). Pouomogne (2008) investigated on capture-based aquaculture of *Clarias* catfish as a case study of the Santchou fishers in Nkam River basin in the western and littoral provinces of Cameroon. In Egypt, Saleh (2006) reported the use of wild-caught mullet seed for the annual restocking of inland lakes. Samuel and Nyambi (2013), evaluated the growth response of wild *C. gariepinus* fingerling procured from the Ndongo stream in Buea (Cameroun), fed dried maggot as protein source and concluded that *C. gariepinus* fingerlings harvested from the wild could tolerate (100%) inclusion of dried maggot meal in the diet in place of fishmeal.

This study is conducted to evaluate and compare the growth performance, food utilisation and survival of *C. gariepinus* fingerlings collected from the wild and hatchery.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study area

Wild fingerlings of *C. gariepinus* were collected from the Cross River Basin (Ayadehe Village, along Itu Head Bridge) at Itu Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. (Latitude 5° 10' N and Longitude 8° 3' E). The area is bounded in the North by Cross River State, West by Ibiono Ibom Local Government Area, East by Uruan Local Government Area., and South by Uyo Local Government Area. The river rises from the Cameroon mountains and flows south-westwards into the Atlantic Ocean (Isangedighi and Umoumoh, 2011). Hatchery bred fingerlings were collected from the Institute of Oceanography fish farm hatchery complex, University of Calabar, Cross River State of Nigeria. It is located in the city of Calabar at approximately latitude 4°8'N and longitude 8°20'E within the mangrove environment and rain forest and of Southeast Nigeria. (Akpanet al., 2002).

Experimental fish

A total of forty (40) fingerlings of *C. gariepinus* was used for this study. Twenty (20) hatchery bred fingerlings of *C. gariepinus* collected from the University of Calabar Hatchery Complex, Nigeria and twenty (20) wild fingerlings collected from Ayadehe Village (Itu Head Bridge), Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Experimental design

This research work was conducted in duplicate for 10 weeks where four aquaria measuring 96 by 50 by 29 cm³ were used. Twenty (20) hatchery bred fingerlings of *C. gariepinus* collected from the University of Calabar Hatchery complex were stocked in Aquarium A₁ and A₂ (10 in each Aquarium). Twenty (20) wild fingerlings of *Clarias gariepinus* collected from Ayadehe Village (Itu Head Bridge) and stocked in Aquarium B₁ and B₂ (10 in each Aquarium). The stocked fish were acclimated for two weeks prior to the start of the experiment (Eyo and Ekanem, 2011). Before the start of the experiment, the initial weight of the fish was measured with METLAR MD-2000 electronic weighing balance while the initial length was measured using measuring board. These measurements were repeated after every two weeks for 10 weeks. Fish were fed with Coppens feed at 5% of their body weight twice daily throughout the experimental period (Ekanem et al., 2012).

Proximate composition of the experimental feed (Coppens feed)

Proximate analysis of the dry matter of the experimental feed (Coppens feed) was performed according to A.O.A.C. (2000), in the Department of Biochemistry, University of Calabar.

Growth performance indices

Growth performance indices were evaluated according to Eyo and Ekanem (2011) as shown below:

- i. Mean wet weight gain (g): Final weight (W_2) – Initial weight (W_1)
- ii. Length gain (cm): Final length (L_2) – Initial length (L_1)
- iii. Growth rate ($\frac{g}{day}$): (Final weight – Initial weight)/(Number of days)
- iv. Specific growth rate ($\frac{\%}{day}$): $(\ln \text{ final weight}) - (\ln \text{ initial weight}) / (\text{Number of days}) \times 100$
- v. Mean growth rate ($\frac{mg}{day}$): $[(\text{final wt} - \text{Initial wt}) / 0.5(\text{final wt} + \text{Initial wt})(\text{Number of days})] \times 1000$
- vi. % survival: $[(\text{Number of fish survived}) / (\text{Number of fish stocked})] \times 100$
- vii. Percentage weight gain (%): $(\text{Final weight} - \text{Initial Weight} / \text{Final Weight}) \times 100$

Physicochemical parameters

Water quality parameters measured include pH, dissolved oxygen, temperature and ammonia. pH and dissolved oxygen was measured using pH and oxygen meter, temperature was measured using thermometer while ammonia was be measured colorimetrically using ammonia test kit (David et al., 2010).

Statistical analysis

Growth performance and food utilization data like mean weight gain (g), length gain (cm), growth rate (g/day), mean growth rate (mg/day), specific growth rate (%/day), Percentage weight gain (%), food conversion ratio (FCR), food conversion efficiency (%) and % survival were subjected to one way analysis of variance (ANOVA) to determine the significant difference using PASW windows software program for statistical analysis (version 18.0). Effects with a probability of ($P < 0.05$) were considered significant.

Statement of hypothesis

Null Hypothesis (H_0): There is no significant difference between the growth performance, food utilisation and survival of hatchery bred fingerlings and wild collected fingerlings of *C. gariepinus*

Alternative Hypothesis (H_1): There is significant difference between the growth performance, food utilisation and survival of hatchery bred fingerlings and wild collected fingerlings of *C. gariepinus*.

RESULTS

Mean proximate analysis of Coppens feed

Mean proximate analysis (Fig. 3) of the experimental feed (Coppens feed) shows that moisture content was (8.23 ± 0.07), mean crude protein content (42.94 ± 1.34), mean lipid content (11.57 ± 0.15), mean crude fibre content (3.53 ± 0.31), mean ash content (9.42 ± 0.04) and mean carbohydrate content (24.31 ± 2.10).

Mean bi-weekly cumulative weight gain

Figure 1: Mean bi-weekly cumulative weight gain (g) of hatchery bred and wild collected fingerlings of *C. gariepinus*.

Mean bi-weekly cumulative weight gain (Fig.1) was obtained from the bi-weekly growth performance of the hatchery bred and wild collected fingerlings of *C. gariepinus*. The cumulative weight gain at the last week gives the total weight gain for the experimental period. For hatchery bred fingerlings, mean cumulative weight gain increased from $0 \pm 0.0\text{g}$ in week 0 to 79.5 ± 2.5 (week 2), to $196.5 \pm 6.5\text{g}$ (week 4), to $367.0 \pm 11.0\text{g}$ (week 6), to 554.0 ± 3.0 (week 8) and 657.5 ± 2.5 (week 10). For wild fingerlings, mean cumulative weight gain increased from $0 \pm 0.0\text{g}$ in week 0 to $40.0 \pm 1.0\text{g}$ (week 2), to $121.0 \pm 3.0\text{g}$ (week 4), to $208.5 \pm 4.5\text{g}$ (week 6), to 288.0 ± 8.0 (week 8) and 6411.0 ± 6.0 (week 10).

Mean bi-weekly cumulative length gain

Figure 2: Mean bi-weekly cumulative length gain (cm) of hatchery bred and wild collected fingerlings of *C. gariepinus*.

Figure 3: Mean proximate composition of experimental feed (Coppens feed)

Mean bi-weekly cumulative length gain (Fig. 2) was obtained from the bi-weekly growth performance of the hatchery bred and wild collected fingerlings of *C. gariepinus*. The cumulative length gain at the last week gives the total length gain for the experimental period. For hatchery bred fingerlings , mean cumulative length gain increased from $0 \pm$

0.0cm in week 0; to 4.95 ± 0.05 cm (week 2), to 8.0 ± 0.1 cm (week 4), to 10.65 ± 0.15 cm (week 6), to 13.25 ± 0.15 cm (week 8) and 16.15 ± 0.15 cm (week 10). For wild fingerlings, mean cumulative length gain increased from 0 ± 0.0 cm in week 0; to 1.1 ± 0.1 cm (week 2), to 5.8 ± 0.1 cm (week 4), to 8.4 ± 0.10 cm (week 6), to 9.75 ± 0.05 cm (week 8) and 11.55 ± 0.15 cm (week 10).

Mean growth performance indices of hatchery bred and wild collected fingerlings of *C. gariepinus*

TABLE 1: mean growth performance indices of hatchery bred and wild collected fingerlings of *C. gariepinus*

Growth Performance Indices	Hatchery Collected Fingerlings	Wild Collected Fingerlings
Mean initial weight (g)	45.0 ± 0.0	45.0 ± 0.0
Mean final weight (g)	702.5 ± 2.5	456.0 ± 6.0
Mean weight gain (g)	657.5 ± 2.5	411.0 ± 6.0
Mean initial length (cm)	6.5 ± 0.1	6.5 ± 0.0
Mean final length (cm)	22.15 ± 0.15	17.55 ± 0.15
Mean length gain (cm)	16.15 ± 0.15	11.55 ± 0.15
Growth rate (GR)	9.40 ± 0.04	5.86 ± 0.10
SGR	3.93 ± 0.01	3.31 ± 0.02
MGR	25.12 ± 0.00	23.44 ± 0.06
PWG	93.60 ± 0.30	90.13 ± 0.13
% Survival	95.0 ± 5.0	85.0 ± 5.0

The growth performance indices (Table 1) evaluated using weight gain (g), length gain (cm), growth rate (GR), specific growth rate (SGR), mean growth rate (MGR) and percentage weight gain (PWG) and % survival. Mean weight gain (g) was higher in hatchery bred fingerlings (657.5 ± 2.5 g) than wild collected fingerlings (411.0 ± 6.0 g). Length gain (cm) also followed from the same pattern with hatchery bred fingerlings showing higher result (16.15 ± 0.15 cm) than fingerlings collected from the wild (11.55 ± 0.15 cm). Growth rate (GR) was also higher in hatchery bred fingerlings (9.40 ± 0.04 gday⁻¹) than wild collected fingerlings (5.86 ± 0.10 gday⁻¹). Specific growth rate (SGR) and mean growth rate (MGR) also followed the same pattern with hatchery bred fingerling having higher values (3.93 ± 0.01 %day⁻¹) for specific growth rate (SGR) and (25.12 ± 0.00 mgday⁻¹) for mean growth rate (MGR) than wild collected fingerlings showing lower values (3.31 ± 0.02 %day⁻¹) for specific growth rate (SGR) and (23.44 ± 0.06 mgday⁻¹) for mean growth rate (MGR). Percentage weight gain (PWG) also followed the same trend with hatchery bred fingerlings showing higher value (93.60 ± 0.03 %) than wild collected fingerling value (90.13 ± 0.13 %). Mean % survival also followed the same pattern with hatchery bred fingerling showing higher value (95 ± 5.0) than fingerling collected from the wild (85 ± 5).

Food utilisation indices of hatchery bred and wild collected fingerlings *C. gariepinus*

TABLE 2: Food utilisation indices of hatchery bred and wild collected fingerlings

Food utilization indices	Hatchery Collected Fingerlings	Wild Collected Fingerlings
Food Consumed (g)	993.15 ± 14.85	617.75 ± 11.55
FCR	1.51 ± 0.02	1.50 ± 0.05
FCE	66.22 ± 0.74	66.54 ± 0.23

Food utilization indices (Table 2) evaluated using food conversion ratio (FCR) and food conversion efficiency (FCE) showed that hatchery bred fingerlings had food conversion ratio (FCR) of 1.51 ± 0.02 and food conversion efficiency (FCE) of $66.95 \pm 0.82\%$ while wild fingerlings had a food conversion ratio (FCR) of 1.50 ± 0.05 and food conversion efficiency (FCE) of $66.54 \pm 2.39\%$. Food consumed was higher in hatchery bred fingerlings ($993.15 \pm 14.85\text{g}$) than wild collected fingerlings ($617.75 \pm 11.55\text{g}$).

Mean water quality parameters

TABLE 3: Mean water quality parameters

	HATCHERY BRED FINGERLING	WILD FINGERLINGS	COLLECTED
pH	7.1±0.1	7.0±0.2	
Water temperature (°C)	28.0±0.4	28.4±0.2	
Ammonia (mg/l)	0.005± 0.001	0.005± 0.002	
Dissolved Oxygen (mg/l)	3.2 ±0 .2	3.0 ±0 .1	

Results of the mean water quality parameters are shown in Table 3. In Aquarium A₁ and A₂ where hatchery bred fingerlings were reared, mean pH was 7.1 ± 0.1 , mean water temperature ($28.0 \pm 0.4^\circ\text{C}$), mean dissolved oxygen ($3.2 \pm 0.2 \text{ mg/l}$) and mean ammonia ($0.005 \pm 0.001\text{mg/l}$). In Aquarium B₁ and B₂ where wild collected fingerlings were reared, mean pH was 7.0 ± 0.2 , mean water temperature ($28.4 \pm 0.2^\circ\text{C}$); mean dissolved oxygen ($3.0 \pm 0.1 \text{ mg/l}$) and mean ammonia ($0.005 \pm 0.002\text{mg/l}$).

DISCUSSION

African catfish (*C. gariepinus*) exhibits considerable growth variation both under aquaculture and in the wild (Van der Waal, 1998). According to Aderolu et al. (2011), the causes of such variation are still not clear, although it has been suggested that inherent differences in feeding behaviour may contribute to this variation (Valente et al., 2001; Sundström et al., 2003; Martins et al., 2005). In the present study, it was observed that hatchery bred fingerlings acclimatized faster to the aquaculture conditions in terms of acceptability of artificial feed.

This may be attributed to the type of feed used (Coppens) for the present study and also to the fact that Coppens feed was used as the first exogenous feed in feeding hatchery bred fish immediately after absorption of their yolk sac.

In terms of growth performance, weight gain, length gain, growth rate, SGR, MGR and PWG was significantly higher ($P < 0.05$) in hatchery bred fingerlings than fingerlings obtained from the wild. Findings from the present study agree with Ekanem et al. (2012) who reported that *C. gariepinus* respond aggressively to Coppens feed as a result of its palatability attributed to its composition. Also, Coppens feed has a more fishy odour that makes it very inviting to fish and also its floatable nature. This observation is similar to Agokei et al. (2011) who reported that commercial fish feeds such as Coppens, Multifeed, Vital and Euro, emits stronger fishy odours and considering the fact that *C. gariepinus* makes use of the olfactory senses during feeding. Proximate analysis of the experimental feed (Coppens feed) shows that moisture content (8.23 ± 0.07), crude protein content (42.94 ± 1.34), lipid content (11.57 ± 0.15), crude fibre content (3.53 ± 0.31), ash content (9.42 ± 0.04) and carbohydrate content (24.31 ± 2.10), were adequate for optimal growth of *C. gariepinus* (Agokei et al., 2011). The observed lipid value in this study is in line with that of Cowey and Sargent (1979) who reported that in general, 10-20% of lipid in most freshwater fish diets gives optimal growth rates without producing an excessively fatty carcass. Findings obtained in this study agrees with Ayuba and Iorkohol (2013) who reported that the nutrient balance of feed influences feed utilization and growth of fish. Also, Hasan (2001) reported that the supply of inputs (feeds, fertilizers etc.) has to be ensured so that the nutrients and energy requirements of the species under cultivation are met and the production goals of the system are achieved.

Amount of feed consumed by hatchery bred fingerlings was significantly higher ($P < 0.05$) than that of wild collected fingerlings. The availability of suitable diets that are effectively digested and provide the required nutrient for optimum growth is a key component of fish nutrition (Mokolensang et al., 2003). Results from this study showed that wild collected fingerlings grew slower than hatchery collected fish with depressed growth compared to hatchery-reared fish as a result of consuming less feed. This findings disagrees with Sundström and Johnsson (2001); Johnsen and Ugedal (1986, 1989, 1990) who reported that hatchery-reared brown trout ate less and were slower to

attack prey and were less efficient in consuming live novel prey compared with wild conspecifics in a laboratory study. In the present study, the reduced growth performance of wild collected fingerlings compared to hatchery bred fish may thus be attributed to a lack of experience of feeding on artificial feed. Bohlin et al. (2002) observed that prior-residence effect may lead to initial poor performance of fish released from one environment to another.

In the present study, it was observed that wild fingerlings accepted artificial after three weeks from start of experiment. This may be responsible for the slow growth rate of the wild fingerlings as shown in the bi-weekly cumulative length and weight gain (Fig. 1 and 2) when compared to hatchery bred fingerlings. This is an indication that *C. gariepinus* is a hardy fish species that can withstand starvation and tolerate harsh environmental conditions like muddy, turbid and oxygen depleted water bodies with the help of their accessory air-breathing organ that allows them to breathe atmospheric oxygen (Eyo and Ekanem, 2011). This could also be responsible for non-significant ($P>0.05$) percentage survival observed in this study. This hardy nature of wild collected *C. gariepinus* could be attributed to the fact that in natural habitats, artificial feed are unavailable and fishes depends primarily on natural food such as insects, plankton, snails and plant matter in the natural water bodies (Ugwumba and Abumoye, 1990). This could be the major reason of growth variation exhibited by *C. gariepinus* both under aquaculture and in the wild (Van der Waal, 1998).

However, fast growth observed in hatchery bred fish in this study may be attributed to the health status of the brood fish used in producing fingerlings in the University of Calabar hatchery complex.

Ekanem et al., (2010) highlighted that growth and feed conversion ratio of a fish is a remarkable tool to compute the acceptability of artificial feed. In the present study, feed conversion ratio (FCR) and feed conversion efficiency (FCE) of hatchery bred fingerling was not significantly different from wild collected fingerlings. This indicates source of fingerlings does not influence FCE and FCR of *C. gariepinus*.

According to Bolivar et al. (2008), temperature and other environmental factors dictate the progress of growth of the fish whether it will be at its optimum or not. When desirable levels of these factors are reached, growth will take place and if possible, optimum growth will be attained. In the present study, water quality parameters including pH, temperature, dissolved oxygen and ammonia were maintained at optimum level recommended by Boyd (1979) for both treatments.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The present study has revealed that hatchery bred fingerlings of *C. gariepinus* acclimate faster to culture condition compared with wild collected fingerlings. Wild collected fish responded positively to artificial feed after three weeks of culture which led to a slow growth compared with hatchery bred fish. The implication of this findings is that hatchery bred fingerlings of *C. gariepinus* still remains the best source of fingerlings supply for fish farmers. It is therefore concluded that fish farmers who still rely on wild fingerlings for stocking of ponds will be faced with problems like poor growth performance and negative response to artificial feed during the first few weeks of culture. This may lead to stunted fish, increase in culture period and reduction in expected profit margin.

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